

Guidelines for online systems and platforms

WP5

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¹ PU = Public
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Guidelines for online systems and platforms

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GLOSSARY / LIST OF ACRONYMS

Glossary

Within this document, the terms “digital solution”, “digital platform”, “online portal”, “web application”, “online solution”, “online platform” are used interchangeably.

When dealing with the digital platform, “patients” are preferably referred to as “participants”. However, some exceptions have been maintained, namely: tables and text directly delivered by VL often use “patients” and have been maintained unchanged; table in Annex 6.1 (List of C4D pilot implementers), which uses “patients”, is part of the C4D official documentation and has been reported unchanged; any occurrence of “patient’s electronic health record” has been reported unchanged since this is the correct definition of the tool; any occurrence of “patients” not referred to the participation to the digital platform has been maintained unchanged.

“1-level authorization” is a simple mode to gain access to digital interfaces and contents, and it is only based, usually, on the input of a username and a password, while a “2-level authorization” is more secure and requires an additional check, which may be a code sent through a SMS, a code delivered as a OTP (one time password), a biometrics check (finger, face, voice,..).

List of acronyms

AE: Affiliated Entity

BP: Best Practice

C4D: Care4Diabetes

D5.3: Deliverable 5.3

GANTT: Gantt Chart (timeline of the project)

GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation

IEC: International Electrotechnical Commission

ISS: Istituto Superiore di Sanità (Italian National Institute of Health)

IT: Information Technology

JA: Joint Action

M6: month 6 (of the project)

MS: Microsoft

NGO: non-governmental organization

SC: Steering Committee

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T5.3: Task 5.3

TBD: to be defined

VL: Voeding Leeft (owner of the Best Practice “ReverseDiabetes2Now”)

WP5: Work Package 5

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Joint Action Care4Diabetes (C4D) aims at exploiting the approach and the methods of the Best Practice “ReverseDiabetes2Now”, owned by the NGO Voeding Leeft (VL), to implement local programmes (pilots) through which investigating its transferability, feasibility and sustainability at Country level. The Best Practice, which addresses the improvement of lifestyle and therapy management of patients with type 2 Diabetes and overweight or obesity, mainly relies on both in-presence and online programmes, the latter delivered through a dedicated digital platform (the VL digital platform can be visited at <https://reverseddiabetes2now.com/>). Through the platform, a multi-disciplinary, trained team of health professionals is meant to digitally interact with the participants and to manage clinical and self-reported data. The platform is not expected to be used during the in-presence days of the C4D programme or for the in-person version of the BP (not planned within the C4D pilots); however, its approach, tools and contents might be helpfully exploited as well.

Each implementer Country within C4D needs to adopt a digital solution to deliver the programme of the pilot studies. Within T5.3, ISS has been working since the beginning of the JA to support all implementers through: the analysis and a detailed description of the VL platform’s main functions; the identification of key-elements of a C4D online portal; the characterization of the state of the art at each Country with respect to the digital solution adoption; the possible pros and cons of the proposed platforms, applications and devices, with special focus on the compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR 2016/679); the sharing of approach and core elements of the ISS digital platform under construction, once tested for feasibility; the eventual hosting of some Partners’ digital platforms within the ISS IT framework to allow the in-time execution of all the pilots.

Basically, the VL digital platform acts as an “all-in-one” platform which addresses the management of: participants’ clinical data; participants’ self-reported data (monitoring functions); activities, resources, and community-based interactions among the participants and with the multidisciplinary team’s members (social interaction). Clinical data management is critical since it deals with participants’ personal, sensible data and shall fully comply with the GDPR as for data security, privacy, availability and integrity. This management can either be performed within a regional/national health information system, or implemented via a dedicated platform which shall however act through secure authentication procedures. Monitoring of self-reported data is used by participants and the team to track changes along the programme, and

shall rely on secure questionnaires and tools. The social interaction features are instead meant to facilitate the interaction among participants and between participants and the team, the participants' consultation of helpful contents, the assignment of calendar activities or the delivery of webinars. Supervision is needed by the team to avoid the dissemination of unsuitable or even risky contents and messages; data security and privacy shall be guaranteed as well; participants shall always be informed on the level of possible dissemination of their data and shall deliver their signed consent.

Within the C4D, and according to each implementer Country's resources and context, the above three main groups of functions – clinical data management, self-reported data monitoring, and social interaction - can be delivered either by means of an “all-in-one” dedicated platform or via separated, ad-hoc or adapted from existing, digital solutions.

A first survey was conducted at month 3 (April 2023) among the 14 pilot implementers, to first investigate the state of the art of the identification of a suitable digital solution.

ISS collected and shared information (through webinars, documents and demos) about possible advantages and risks of each mentioned digital solution (detailed in the next paragraphs).

A second, short survey was then administered by ISS afterwards (June 2023), to collect updated implementers' position/decision. The activity is still ongoing.

ISS shared with the Partners its own approach and the main features of the Moodle-based digital platform which resulted feasible, and which is currently under preparation to deliver the programmes of the C4D Italian pilots. The explanatory documentation is reported and briefly discussed in this Document, even though it is not yet consolidated. Likely, ISS will also host 3 Partners' platforms to allow them to start the pilots on time.

The present document should be intended as a dynamic document, which will be completed with a full description of all the adopted solutions once they will be tested and ready to use. The information presented in this deliverable will be further complemented in the deliverables D6.2 (Report on Phase I intensive programme) and D7.1 (Report on Phase II after-care activities).

1. PURPOSE AND OBJECTIVES

The purpose of Task 5.3 is to coordinate and foster the development of the online portals at each pilot implementer site. The purpose of the present Deliverable (D5.3) is thus to guide the preparation of digital platforms suitable to transfer and deliver the BP at Country level and to investigate its feasibility and appropriateness within national scenarios.

Actions behind this Deliverable needed to start at the very beginning of the JA, since key-information are urgently needed by the implementers to setup the platforms in time for the implementation of the pilots.

Several actions were conducted in parallel, leaded by ISS and shared with all Partners, to cope with the following objectives:

- to characterize and describe functions, activities, resources, tools, and technical requirements of the VL digital platform;
- to identify key-elements of a suitable C4D digital solution, also including mandatory requirements to cope with data security issues;
- to analyse orientation and resources of each implementer, and the state of the art of the identification of suitable digital solutions;
- to formulate helpful recommendations for local solutions, either temporary for the implementation of the pilots only, or mature enough to maintain the BP programme beyond the JA;
- to test the feasibility of a dedicated digital solution (ISS platform for Italian pilots), to be eventually replicated in/for other Countries.

The present document will report on methods applied to address the above objectives, and relevant results. Within the document, the terms “digital solution”, “digital platform”, “online portal”, “web application”, “online solution”, “online platform” are used interchangeably.

At the current stage of the project (M6), final decisions have not been taken yet, and solutions adopted, by all Countries, thus the hereby reported description of the set of online portals has to be intended as not consolidated.

Even in those cases where the framework of the online portal has been already decided and prepared, the contents to be used during the C4D pilot programmes, in line with the project

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GANTT, are still under preparation, thus their detailed description remains out of the scope of this document.

Functional tests of the online portals, as well as training materials to ensure the proper use of the portals by all users – participants and health professionals – will be respectively executed and prepared in the following months. Thus, only a suitable approach to guide their design is suggested in the document.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. CHARACTERIZATION OF THE VL PLATFORM

The ISS strategy to characterize the VL digital platform relied on the following actions and resources:

- analysis of the project documentation, mainly focussing on key-elements of the expected C4D digital solution, among which: the hosting IT infrastructure; the development environment; interaction, accessibility and security issues; tools to manage participants' registration, activities, resources and data; technology requirements;
- analysis of the project documentation, to define how the VL platform addresses each key-element of the VL BP programme, and to describe each eventual additional feature;
- surfing of the VL platform once two ISS accounts had been created to log in a demo section of the VL platform;
- checklist of specific questions to VL personnel, exchanged by emails;
- online meetings: ad-hoc meetings with VL and the JA Coordinator or plenary meetings (SC, Pilot implementers, or WP5 meetings).
- use and guided exploration of the VL platform during the VL "Train the Trainers" course: 2 ISS IT experts, which are also acting as members of the Italian multi-disciplinary team, could go deeper into the knowledge of all the platform features, under the guidance of the VL team.

VL characterization activities started in a pre-work phase of the project (i.e. before the official start of the project), and lasted until the end of the First Round of the VL "Train the trainers" course, namely June 28th 2023.

2.2. KEY-ELEMENTS OF THE C4D DIGITAL SOLUTION

To identify key-elements of the digital solution, also including mandatory requirements to cope with data security issues, the strategy consisted of the integration of the available sources of information, namely:

- the characterization of the VL digital platform;
- the outcomes of the several ongoing activities of the project, especially the agreed definition of the study protocol; this helped to clarify which features and sections of the VL platform shall be included in the C4D portals, which might be abandoned, and which features shall be eventually added;

- the limitations reported by some implementers to deliver on time a consolidated and effective digital solution;
- the requirements needed by the expected compliance at least with GDPR (other, more restrictive laws may also be in force at Country level).

Key-elements were summarized and further explained during online meetings with the implementers; in particular, demos were prepared for a meeting held on June 22nd, to show feasibility, pros and cons of some proposed digital solutions to all project participants.

2.3. IMPLEMENTERS' STATE OF THE ART OF THE DIGITAL SOLUTION

The strategy to address this issue was mainly based on:

- the preparation of a synthetic description of main functions and technical requirements of the VL's and the expected C4D online portals; this description was explained to the pilot implementers during the biweekly, recorded online meetings, and included in documents uploaded in the proper folder of the Teams JA repository;
- the preparation and the delivery of a checklist (open questions) to collect information from the implementers about the state of the art of their local, country-related scenario with respect to possible adoption of a suitable digital platform. Questions addressed: the availability and readiness of a platform; the level of adaptations required; the intention to develop a new, dedicated platform; the intention to use other, provisional means to deliver the C4D programme; the availability of local resources and possible impairments to develop a new platform; the local level of knowledge of crucial issues like data security and compliance with GDPR. The checklist was uploaded to the proper Pilot folder of the C4D Teams repository; the associated activity was created and scheduled on Click-Up, and messages and reminders reached the implementers until the deadline (April 30th 2023);
- the analysis of the compiled checklists, preparation and sharing of a synthesis also including the list of hypothesized solutions, either customized or available on the market. A proper search and some feasibility tests were then performed by the ISS Team to clarify pros and cons of each proposed solution; main outcomes of this activity were added to the synthesis document;

- an ISS Webinar to implementers, to discuss the relevant results included in the synthesis document, and to give the implementers additional means to refine or better define their proposal for a digital solution;
- a final, short survey was prepared and delivered, based on pre-defined possible answers, to collect the updated feedback by the implementers and to check whether all of them solved the most critical issues so as to likely have their digital solution ready for the start of the pilot studies (proposed deadline June 30th 2023, but still ongoing at the date of July 24th).

2.4. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR LOCAL DIGITAL SOLUTIONS

To formulate helpful recommendations for local solutions, many aspects were considered, certainly including the following:

- the intended temporary or long-lasting use of the platform, i.e. whether the platform is only intended to be used for the C4D pilot implementation (due to possible discard, upgrade or replacement afterwards), or rather the implementer is aiming at a more consolidated solution and the BP programme's eventual sustainability beyond the JA;
- the availability, at Country level, of technical, human, and economic resources to dedicate to the C4D digital platform setup (possibly including design, construction, testing, managing, and maintenance);
- the implementation of a programme delivery approach comparable with the VL BP programme in terms of activities, resources, ease of use, accessibility and compliance with GDPR. Extremely relevant, motivational aspects should be always kept in mind, to encourage the participants to start the programme, to enhance their motivation during the intensive phase of the programme, and to hopefully keep a high level of adherence during the follow-up phase;
- the compliance, as far as possible, with the open-source approach.

The documentation prepared during the previous steps of Task 5.3 (see previous paragraphs) was finally completed with motivated opinions by the ISS team of IT technology experts.

2.5. FEASIBILITY OF THE ISS DIGITAL SOLUTION

The design of the ISS digital solution actually was initiated before the official start of the project. At the time of the submission of the proposal, the ISS IT experts participating in the project estimated the human and technical resources needed and hypothesized possible software architectures for the C4D digital platform. Once the project had been approved, the activity was launched, starting with the identification of the most suitable software environment. Critical elements to take the decision included the project timeline, accessibility and security issues, the open-access approach, the personnel experience and skills, human and technical resources required to dedicate to the project, the national scenario of the healthcare digital management.

To test feasibility and appropriateness of the platform: internal bench tests were planned, involving the ISS IT experts; several online meetings were scheduled with the whole professional teams of ISS and Italian Affiliated Entities (AEs) in charge for the pilot implementation; demo contents were prepared; data workflow was simulated also taking into consideration the pilot study protocol; the ISS approach was shared and discussed with the other C4D partners.

3. RESULTS

The characterization of the VL platform (sub-paragraph 3.1) was essential to conduct the residual Task 5.3 activities in parallel, so as to: define in detail the key-elements of the C4D digital solution (sub-paragraph 3.2); deliver basic information to the implementers and give them the means to hypothesize a local digital solution (sub-paragraph 3.3); prepare and share recommendations for local digital solutions (sub-paragraph 3.4); work on the ISS Moodle-based solution, by purposely developing and testing software codes for eventual, missing tools or tools that needed adaptation, and by investigating its feasibility (sub-paragraph 3.5).

3.1. CHARACTERIZATION OF THE VL PLATFORM

Following the analysis of the C4D project documentation, the surfing of the VL platform, the VL team explanation at the C4D Kick-off meeting and additional clarifications during online meetings, a list of residual questions was prepared by ISS and answered by VL (March 28th – April 4th, 2023). Results of this fruitful interaction are reported in Table 1.

Table 1 – Characterization of the VL platform – residual questions (by ISS) and answers (by VL)

Residual questions (ISS)	Answers (VL)
Which personal data do you store?	<p>2 streams:</p> <p>1: patient data: collected as part of the application process via a secure application form or a secure referral system - contact information (name, address, email address, telephone number) and medical information (blood glucose information, diabetes medication)</p> <p>2: patient self-reported data: collected via the community platform and used by the patients and the support team to track progress - blood glucose level, weight and waist circumference.</p> <p>In addition, the patient email address is stored and used as the username to access the community</p>

<p>How do you reach the compliance with GDPR (including issues like data security&privacy&integrity&availability, cookies management, informed consent,..)?</p>	<p>We use Salesforce as a patient information system and this is a secure system with 2-factor authentication where it is possible to ensure that users only have access to the data they need for their role</p> <p>The community is built with additional security and participants only have access to their own data and the support team only have access to their group's information</p> <p>We ask for informed consent as part of the application process for the program and have a clear privacy policy including on the use of cookies</p>
<p>Which of the listed data are uploaded by the participant and which by the doctor?</p>	<p>Doctor: relevant medical history, diabetes medication and other medication if relevant, lab results HbA1c, cholesterol and kidney function, blood pressure</p> <p>Participant: blood glucose level, weight and waist circumference. Status of exercise, relaxation and sleep</p>
<p>Are you asking the participant to also upload clinical data from blood lab examination?</p>	<p>Yes, we ask them to complete a secure questionnaire to provide information on weight, waist circumference, HbA1c and diabetes medication after 3,6,12,18,24 months</p>
<p>Which data has the participant access to?</p>	<p>The data they share on the community platform - weight, waist circumference and blood glucose data</p>
<p>Which devices does the participant use to interact with your platform (smartphone/tablet/notebook/other)?</p>	<p>Most patients use a laptop or desktop computer or a tablet. It is possible to participate on a smartphone but it is not ideal</p>
<p>Which data can the participant download from the platform?</p>	<p>The patient can't download the data from the platform. The patient can request a</p>

	copy of their data and it will be provided via secure mail
Is the platform compliant with other laws (i.e. accessibility, IEC standards..)?	Yes

The description of the VL platform was then shared with the C4D implementers, with a suitable level of detail, through text documents (“T5.3 Technical info on Digital Platform Implementation v1”; “T5.3 ISS simplified description of VL digital platform”; April 2023), power-point presentations (June 22nd 2023 webinar) and live interactions (bi-weekly SC, WP5 and Pilot Implementers’ online meetings). All documents have been made available through the dedicated C4D Teams folder. Most relevant features and functions of the VL online portal are described in Table 2.

Table 2 – Characterization of the VL platform – Most relevant features and functions to implement the BP “ReverseDiabetes2Now”. In the whole Table, patients with type 2 Diabetes are interchangeably referred to as “patients” or “participants” since it is the original text delivered by VL

Item	Description
Aim	<p>To deliver the BP programme mainly through:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • participants’ enrolment (following clinical and motivational assessment) • clinical data management (partially accessible to participants) • clinicians/health professionals’ interaction (not accessible to participants) • clinicians/health professionals’ and participants’ interaction (live webinars or classes, social interaction (community), activities’ scheduling and assignment) • self-reported monitoring data management • delivery of verified contents on lifestyle pillars (nutrition, exercise (physical activity), relaxation, sleep)
Environment and architecture. Compliance with GDPR (data	Dedicated, web-based application, developed on purpose by a committed Software-House.

<p>security, privacy, integrity and availability, cookies management, informed consent,..); accessibility; ...</p>	<p>A secure patient information system (Salesforce) guarantees for secure access based on 2-factor authentication and tailored to the different roles (support team or participant).</p> <p>Additional security procedures are applied to the community environment, again with access permission associated with the role (i.e. participants only have access to their own data and multi-media materials of the programme).</p> <p>Informed consent is mandatory as part of the application process.</p> <p>Privacy policy, including the use of cookies, is clearly reported.</p> <p>Besides GDPR compliance on data security, privacy and integrity (reached through the above-mentioned adopted measures), data availability is also guaranteed: participants can't straight download the data from the platform, but they can request a copy of their data, which is provided by VL via secure mail.</p> <p>The online portal is compliant with accessibility, IT and IEC standards.</p> <p>The platform is accessible 24hours/7days; technical assistance (help-desk) is available on-demand to solve issues associated with the technology (network; systems; devices; contents' accessibility; other)</p>
<p>Groups of functions</p>	<p>Main functions of the VL online portal can be grouped as functions for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clinical data management: at the beginning of the application for the programme, patient's data are collected as part of the application process via a secure application form or a secure referral system - contact information (name, address, email address, telephone number) and medical information (blood glucose information, diabetes medication); other relevant clinical data are collected during the successive steps of the programme by clinicians - relevant medical history, diabetes medication and other medication if relevant, lab results including HbA1c, cholesterol and kidney function, blood pressure. Interaction among clinicians (patient's reference doctors and VL support team) is included among the relevant functions of the clinical data management. • Self-reported data monitoring: patient self-reported data are collected via the community platform following a scheduled or occasional assignment or based on a spontaneous patient's initiative; they are used by the patients and the support team

	<p>to track progress, and mainly consist of blood glucose level, weight and waist circumference, status of exercise, relaxation and sleep. Additionally, patients are asked to complete a secure questionnaire to provide information on weight, waist circumference, HbA1c and diabetes medication after 3,6,12,18,24 months.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social and programme interaction: as part of the community platform, patients are supported through the whole programme via always available multi-media material (hints and suggestions on the lifestyle pillars of nutrition, exercise, relaxation and sleep), tools for social interaction, assigned classes or live webinars. Patients are encouraged to contribute with own experiences, but submitted contents are supervised by the VL support team before publication.
<p>Clinical data management – Main tools, functions and requirements</p>	<p>Functions allow the:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • management of participants’ clinical data • interaction among the clinical/support team’s members • registration and enrolment procedures (application process) <p>Main tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tools for 2-factor authentication process • Tools for registration • Tools for uploading files containing clinical history, clinical examinations, imaging, signed informed consent (at least pdf and text format, usual diagnostic images formats, usual graphic formats) • Tools for administration of secure surveys • Usual community tools (at least for chat, email, forum, videocall) <p>Main requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • compliance with GDPR, accessibility and cookies policy • service 24/7 • secure and stable internet connection • helpdesk and support on demand • secure data storage for high number of participants • use of local (Dutch) language, with possible concurrent use of the English language when needed

<p>Self-reported data monitoring – Main tools, functions and requirements</p>	<p>Functions allow the collection and management of self-reported participants’ data</p> <p>Main tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tools for secure surveys administration and data collection (at least 1-factor authentication) • Tools for tracking progress (also graphically) • Tools for collected data management <p>Main requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • compliance with GDPR, accessibility and cookies policy • service 24/7 • secure and stable internet connection • helpdesk and support on demand • secure data storage for high number of participants • use of local (Dutch) language, with possible concurrent use of the English language when needed
<p>Social and programme interaction – Main tools, functions and requirements</p>	<p>Functions allow the:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • administration, update, and management of activities and resources of the programme • interaction among the clinical/support team’s members, among participants, and between participants and the clinicians/support team <p>Main tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tools for 1-factor authentication process • Tools for uploading and managing programme multi-media resources (files, images, links, videos, animations, audios) • Tools for delivering interacting activities (classes, webinars) • Tools for scheduling activities, reminders, suggestions (interactive management of the participant’s agenda/dashboard) • Tools for supervising participants’ contributions • Usual community tools (at least for chat, email, forum, videocall) <p>Main requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • compliance with GDPR, accessibility and cookies policy

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • service 24/7 • secure and stable internet connection • helpdesk and support on demand • secure data storage for high number of participants and for multi-media contributions • secure links to external contributions (i.e. videos or animations freely available on the web) • use of local (Dutch) language, with possible concurrent use of the English language when needed
<p>Technology and skills required</p>	<p>Participants and health professionals are encouraged to access the digital platform through a laptop, or a desktop computer, or a tablet. It is possible to participate on smartphones but it is not ideal.</p> <p>Participants are asked for a reliable and stable internet connection.</p> <p>A basic level of digital literacy is required to allow the participants to log in the platform and securely use it. Training to the use of the platform is however delivered during the in-presence starting days; helpdesk and on-demand technical support is continuously available through the portal.</p>
<p>Summary of BP programme main issues</p>	<p>Following one participant’s registration, assessment of clinical data, clinical history and collection of other lifestyle and behavioural information is performed to detect whether the level of motivation of the participant is high enough to enrol him/her.</p> <p>Participants are organized into groups of 20 individuals.</p> <p>A support team including at least a coach, a doctor, a nurse and a dietician (all trained and expert in the management of type 2 Diabetes) supervises and manages activities and resources of the portal.</p> <p>Through the community platform, participants are asked to complete a secure questionnaire to provide self-reported information on weight, waist circumference, HbA1c and diabetes medication after 3,6,12,18,24 months of the programme.</p> <p>During the intervention phase, participants are encouraged to use the platform and the platform’s contents as much as possible, and the clinical/support team assigns, manages and monitors the online activities according to convenient scheduling and, when needed, on demand.</p>

	During the follow-up phase, participants are free to access and use the platform whenever they want; activities are no longer “mandatory”; the clinical/support team monitors the activity and give assistance when needed.
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3.2. KEY-ELEMENTS OF THE C4D DIGITAL SOLUTION

Key-elements of the C4D digital solution came from the integration of the VL platform main features (Table 2) with the C4D scope and objectives. They are resumed in Table 3, where modifications with respect to the VL platform features have been highlighted.

Table 3 – Key-elements of the C4D digital solution – Most relevant features and functions to implement the BP “ReverseDiabetes2Now” within the C4D Joint Action. Underlined and strikethrough text indicates a change with respect to the VL platform features in Table 2

Item	Description
Aim	<p>To deliver the BP programme mainly through:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • participants’ enrolment (following clinical and motivational assessment) • clinical data management (<u>separately or through the same digital platform</u>; partially accessible to participants) • clinicians/health professionals’ interaction (not accessible to participants) • clinicians/health professionals’ and participants’ interaction (live webinars or classes, social interaction (community), activities’ scheduling and assignment) • self-reported monitoring data management • delivery of verified contents on lifestyle pillars (nutrition, exercise (physical activity), relaxation, sleep) <p><u>Within C4D pilots, participants’ enrolment (following clinical and motivational assessment) is expected to be performed before participants’ registration on the platform.</u></p>
Environment and architecture. Compliance with GDPR	<u>It may be a dedicated, web-based application, developed on purpose,</u>

<p>(data security, privacy, integrity and availability, cookies management, informed consent,...); accessibility; ...</p>	<p><u>or an adaptation from an existing platform,</u> <u>or a set of separate platforms (either existing or developed on purpose) to address the different groups of functions.</u></p> <p>In any case:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a secure patient participant information system shall guarantee for secure access based on 2-factor authentication and tailored to the different roles (support team or participant): <u>clinical data may be managed through local health information systems, through secure links to the latter, or directly within the C4D platform.</u> • additional security procedures shall be applied to the community environment, again with access permission associated with the role (i.e. participants can only have access to their own data and multi-media materials of the programme). • informed consent shall be mandatory as part of the application process. • privacy policy, including the use of cookies, shall be clearly reported. • besides GDPR compliance on data security, privacy and integrity (reached through the above-mentioned adopted measures), data availability (to the participant) shall be also guaranteed. • the online portal shall be compliant with accessibility, IT and IEC standards. • the platform shall be accessible 24hours/7days; technical assistance (help-desk) shall be available on-demand to solve issues associated with the technology (network; systems; devices; contents' accessibility; other).
<p>Groups of functions</p>	<p>Main functions of the VL C4D online portal can be grouped as functions for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clinical data management: <u>for each participant, medical information and history shall be securely managed by the support team, including diabetes medication and other medication if relevant, lab results including HbA1c, cholesterol and kidney function, blood pressure, and other clinical and lifestyle details as established by the C4D pilot</u>

	<p><u>study protocol. Additionally, interaction among health professionals of the support team, and with the reference clinician if external to the team shall represent relevant functions of the clinical data management.</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-reported data monitoring: participant self-reported data are collected via the community platform following a scheduled or occasional assignment or based on a spontaneous participant’s initiative; they are used by the participants and the support team to track progress, and mainly consist of blood glucose level, weight and waist circumference, status of exercise, relaxation and sleep. Additionally, participants can be asked to complete a secure questionnaire to provide information <u>on weight, waist circumference, HbA1c and diabetes medication at specific time points along the C4D pilot intensive or follow-up phase.</u> • Social and programme interaction: as part of the community platform, participants are supported through the whole programme via always available multi-media material (hints and suggestions on the lifestyle pillars of nutrition, exercise, relaxation and sleep), tools for social interaction, assigned classes or live webinars. Patients Participants are encouraged to contribute with own experiences, but submitted contents shall be supervised by the the C4D support team before publication.
<p>Clinical data management – Main tools, functions and requirements</p>	<p>Functions allow the:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • management of participants’ clinical data • interaction among the clinical/support team’s members • registration and enrolment procedures (application process) <p>Main tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tools for 2-factor authentication process • Tools for registration • Tools for uploading files containing clinical history, clinical examinations, imaging, signed informed consent (at least pdf and text format, usual diagnostic images formats, usual graphic formats) • Tools for administration of secure surveys

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usual community tools (at least for chat, email, forum, videocall) <p>Main requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • compliance with GDPR, accessibility and cookies policy • service 24/7 • secure and stable internet connection • helpdesk and support on demand • secure data storage (<u>limited for a temporary solution, for high number of participants in case of an “at-regimen” solution</u>) • use of local (Dutch) language, with possible concurrent use of the English language when needed
<p>Self-reported data monitoring – Main tools, functions and requirements</p>	<p>Functions allow the collection and management of self-reported participants’ data</p> <p>Main tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tools for secure surveys administration and data collection (at least 1-factor authentication) • Tools for tracking progress (also graphically) • Tools for collected data management <p>Main requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • compliance with GDPR, accessibility and cookies policy • service 24/7 • secure and stable internet connection • helpdesk and support on demand • adequate space (either on physical servers or in cloud) to securely store data (<u>a small amount of memory may be sufficient for a temporary solution, while a higher amount of memory is required for high number of participants, as in the case of an “at-regimen” solution</u>) • use of local (Dutch) language, with possible concurrent use of the English language when needed
<p>Social and programme interaction – Main tools, functions and requirements</p>	<p>Functions allow the:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • administration, update, and management of activities and resources of the programme

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • interaction among the clinical/support team’s members, among participants, and between participants and the clinicians/support team <p>Main tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tools for 1-factor authentication process • Tools for uploading and managing programme multi-media resources (files, images, links, videos, animations, audios) • Tools for delivering interacting activities (classes, webinars) • Tools for scheduling activities, reminders, suggestions (interactive management of the participant’s agenda/dashboard) • Tools for supervising participants’ contributions • Usual community tools (at least for chat, email, forum, videocall) <p>Main requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • compliance with GDPR, accessibility and cookies policy • service 24/7 • secure and stable internet connection • helpdesk and support on demand • secure data storage (<u>limited for a temporary solution, for high number of participants in case of an “at-regimen” solution</u>) • secure links to external contributions (i.e. videos or animations freely available on the web) • use of local (Dutch) language, with possible concurrent use of the English language when needed
<p>Technology and skills required</p>	<p>Participants and health professionals are encouraged to access the digital platform through a laptop, or a desktop computer, or a tablet <u>unless the web application is guaranteed as also optimized for smartphones</u>. It is possible to participate on smartphones but it is not ideal.</p> <p>Participants are asked for a reliable and stable internet connection.</p> <p>A basic level of digital literacy is required to allow the participants to log in the platform and securely use it. Training for the use of the platform shall however be delivered during the in-presence starting</p>

	<p>days; helpdesk and on-demand technical support shall be continuously available through the portal.</p>
<p>Summary of C4D BP programme main issues</p>	<p>Following one participant’s registration (<u>after he/she has been scored as enough motivated and eligible for entering the C4D pilot programme</u>), assessment of clinical data, clinical history and collection of other lifestyle and behavioural information is performed to detect whether the level of motivation of the participant is high enough to enrol him/her. relevant clinical data and clinical and lifestyle history are securely collected and managed.</p> <p>Participants are organized into groups of 20 individuals <u>at maximum</u>.</p> <p>A support team including <u>health professionals as judged appropriate by each implementer (suggestion for at least a coach, a doctor, a nurse and a dietician)</u>, all trained and expert in the management of type 2 Diabetes, supervises and manages activities and resources of the portal.</p> <p>Through the community platform, participants are asked to complete a secure questionnaire to provide self-reported information on weight, waist circumference, HbA1c and diabetes medication <u>at specific time point along the C4D programme (either intensive or follow-up phase) after 3,6,12,18,24 months of the programme.</u></p> <p>During the intervention phase, participants are encouraged to use the platform and the platform’s contents as much as possible, and the clinical/support team assigns, manages and monitors the online activities according to convenient scheduling and, when needed, on demand.</p> <p>During the follow-up phase, participants are free to access and use the platform whenever they want; activities are no longer “mandatory”; the clinical/support team monitors the activity and give assistance when needed.</p>

To early support C4D implementers in the process of understanding the C4D platform needs and identifying possible solutions, a simplified, informative version of the defined key-elements of

the digital solution was delivered to the partners and discussed with them during the online meetings and through explanatory documents. In particular:

- the key-features of the VL digital platform were illustrated as grouped into three main sections, respectively dealing with the management of the clinical data, the management of self-reported monitoring data collected during the C4D programme, and the social interaction among expert team and participants including the delivery of multimedia support materials.
- Criticalities of each group of functions were explained and discussed, among which: the need to securely manage clinical and monitoring data and to comply with the GDPR; the need to supervise materials exchanged among the participants and to avoid undesired/unauthorized dissemination of the programme materials.
- Specifically on GDPR, explanations were given about the requirements of the Regulation. Namely, according to GDPR, digital personal data (which include, among the others, clinical, biological and behavioural data) shall always be guaranteed as for security (i.e., policies, methods, and means to protect personal data), privacy (data shall only be accessible to the owner - who can ask for cancel them at any time - and to those formally authorized to their management; data shall only be used for the purposes they have been collected for), integrity (data shall remain unmodified, i.e. no changes or corruption actions shall alter them) and availability (data owner shall access his/her data at any time). The Regulation does not deliver rules to reach the compliance with its requirements. IT services may follow technical standards to reach the goal; in any case each digital solution needs the approval of the Data Protection Officer (DPO) before its release and use. Among the commonly used solutions, worth to mention are: the multi-factor authentication procedures; the different levels of authorization to access data; the mirroring of data storage and the scheduling of very frequent backups; the definition of fault-recovery procedures; the firewall-based protection; the use of encrypted data; the identification of responsibility roles along the digital data management chain; the proper and continuous education and training of IT personnel and users.
- Finally, demos were delivered during the June 22nd online meeting, to show feasibility, pros and cons of some proposed digital solutions, among which: i) the case of the Facebook hidden and private groups was reported, explaining that there is the chance for the Administrator of the group to supervise before publication all those contents from the participants when uploaded in posts or in the “guide” tool, but supervision is not

possible for contents uploaded to the “album” tool; additionally, contents are not fully protected since there is always a way to share them outside the group; last, as already well known, all the materials uploaded to the groups are owned (and used) by Meta; ii) Teams features were explained, commenting on the more protected and more efficient environment for the aims of the C4d pilots; iii) the ISS platform was illustrated (even though still under construction) to discuss issues like security of the moodle-based tools, also with respect to questionnaires; iv) secure tools for surveys were introduced, like Webropol, Limesurvey, Microsoft Forms; v) the possible use of Whatsapp groups was discussed on specific request from Partners, showing the very limited features for data supervision and protection.

3.3. IMPLEMENTERS’ STATE OF THE ART OF THE DIGITAL SOLUTION

To collect preliminary information on the state of the art of the C4D digital solution at each pilot implementing site:

- the document “T5.3 Technical info on Digital Platform Implementation v1” was prepared, anticipated during online meetings, and uploaded on the proper C4D Teams folder while sending a Teams message to all implementers; deadline for receiving feedback was established on April 30th 2023
- C4D Coordinator was informed and requested to support the compilation of the survey
- Click-up supportive reminders were developed by THL team

The document consisted of:

- indications to compile the document
- explanation on scope, objective and content of the document
- introductory description of the VL digital platform and of C4D portal main needs
- list of questions to be answered (Table 4 of this Deliverable)
- references and the List of Implementing Partners

Table 4 – List of questions (open answers expected) to collect technical Information on C4D Digital Platform Implementation

#	Question
1	Partner short name
2	Country
3	Number of pilots' sites
4	Location of each pilot site (for each site please detail the geographical location i.e. City/Area/Region/...)
5	Type of each pilot site (please specify whether it is: a public or private hospital, a public or private healthcare structure different from the hospital, other)
6	Did you plan to use a digital platform for the C4D pilot/pilots? In case you don't want to manage the participants by means of a digital platform, please clarify the way you're going to implement the pilot/pilots and skip questions from 7 to 12.
7	Do you already have a digital platform to host the C4D pilot/pilots? If the answer is "yes", please deliver the relevant information* and describe the main functions. Please add a link in case a public section of the platform is available. *among the relevant information: owner; host; hosting network/environment/systems; current data exchanged; compliance with GDPR and other in-force laws; interacting technology (smartphone, tablet, notebook,..)
8	In case you have a digital platform, please detail the adaptations needed to implement the C4D pilot/pilots. Please pay special attention to possible risks and criticalities, if any.
9	In case of adaptations needed, which is your plan for a solution? Do you need help for specific issues? Please detail, in case.
10	In case you have/are going to adapt a digital platform, are you planning to use it also for collecting all the needed data from the pilot/pilots?
11	In case you haven't a digital platform but you want to use it for managing pilot's participants, please describe your plan/ideas/proposal. Please report here if you have troubles in implementing it. Please also consider any possible restriction dealing with

	software development environment, hardware requirements, network requirements and/or performance.
12	In case you need adaptations/new implementation of the digital platform, have you got technical personnel to work on the platform? Please describe the resources (either internal or outsourcing) and roles (hardware managers, software developers, ...) that you can count on.
13	How did you plan to collect the whole set of data from the pilots? (hopefully, through the digital platform which manages the pilots' participants, but what if you are not using it?)
14	Are you familiar with the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation EU GDPR 2016/679? Are you aware of other restrictions on personal data management which are in force additionally in your country? Please add information or references, in case. Please ask if you need clarifications.
15	In case you already have a digital platform to use/adapt, are you informed about its compliance with GDPR or other local laws?
16	Independently from having/not having a digital platform ready, are there some peculiar features that you would like to <u>have</u> in the C4D digital platform? Please briefly describe them, together with the reason why you feel them helpful.
17	Independently from having/not having a digital platform ready, are there some peculiar features that you would like to <u>avoid</u> in the C4D digital platform? Please briefly describe them, together with the reason why you feel them helpful.
18	If you are going to use a digital platform in C4D, who is going to host and maintain it <u>during the project</u> ? Please comment on possible criticalities to have the platform available 24/7.
19	If you are going to use a digital platform in C4D, who might host and maintain it <u>after the end of the project</u> ?

C4D implementers were also invited to add questions at the end of the list, if they considered them helpful, as well as to add comments, doubts or further clarifications in a free text format.

Surveys from the 14 pilot implementers were received by the deadline and analysed to possibly group their answers, and to define a preliminary set of proposed solutions so as to investigate

their appropriateness. Briefly: 5 implementers preferred to adopt an “all-in-one” solution and implement all functions - clinical data management, self-reported data monitoring, and social and programme interaction - into one platform only but they still hadn’t identified a solution (3 of them were exploring the adaptation of existing solutions, 2 had no proposals yet); 3 implementers were investigating a Moodle-based solution: 2 intended to use the digital solution for all functions (“all-in-one” solution) and 1 for data monitoring and social interaction only; 5 implementers were investigating separate solutions for clinical data management – mainly relying on the existing health information systems - and for the community platform: for the latter, they hypothesized solutions based on Teams and Facebook; only 1 implementer was planning to avoid the use of the digital platform: however, after discussing the issue with the Steering Committee, this solution was judged as not appropriate to assure adequate comparability among the pilots and the implementer agreed to search for a digital solution.

Table 5 and 6 synthesized the above findings.

Table 5 – Summary of answers from the 14 surveys as for country, partner, and classification in terms of digital platform solution existing/non-existing/under examination/other (state of the art at April 2023). The definition “online community” used in the Table refers to both self-reported data monitoring and social and programme interaction.

Country	Partner short name	ISS GROUPS
Belgium	Sciensano	group1a (NO PLATFORM (myDiabby under study); clinical data management and online community through the same platform)
Slovenia	NIJZ	group1a (NO PLATFORM (e-diabetes.si under study); clinical data management and online community through the same platform)
Bulgaria	MoH BG	group1a (NO PLATFORM (Moodle-based or Slack as possible solution under study); clinical data management and online community through the same platform)
Greece	ALEXANDRA	group1b (NO PLATFORM (no solution under study); clinical data management and online community through the same platform)

Slovakia	MoH SR	group1b (NO PLATFORM (no solution under study; waiting for specs); clinical data management and online community through the same platform)
Finland	FDA	group2a (Moodle-based solution; no clinical data management; GPDR compliance guaranteed)
Italy	ISS (+AOUP, ASLROMA2, FPG)	group2b (Moodle-based; clinical data management included (“all-in-one” solution); GPDR compliance guaranteed)
Portugal	DGS	group2b (NO PLATFORM (solution under study with ISS) Moodle-based; clinical data management included (“all-in-one” solution); GPDR compliance guaranteed)
Hungary	NPHC	group3 (NO PLATFORM (under study); clinical data management and online community through separate platforms)
Poland	NFZ	group3 (NO PLATFORM (under study for online community (Academy NFZ, Teams, Facebook closed group)); clinical data management (excel from providers) and online community through separate platforms)
Spain - Asturias	CSPA/SESPA/FICYT	group3 (NO PLATFORM (under study for online community (Teams and a dedicated platform to be decided)); clinical data management (patient' electronic health record in regional health system) and online community through separate platforms)
Spain - Cantabria	SCS-IDIVAL	group3 (NO PLATFORM (under study for online community (dedicated platform to be decided)); clinical data management (patient' electronic health record in regional health system) and online community through separate platforms)
Spain - Galicia	SERGAS	group3 (NO PLATFORM (under study for online community (Lifesize and a dedicated platform to be decided)); clinical data management (patient' electronic

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		health record in regional health system) and online community through separate platforms)
Malta	MFH	group4 (NO INTENTION TO USE DIGITAL PLATFORMS; NO SOLUTION)

Table 6 – Hypothesized solutions and use of existing applications as reported in the surveys compiled by the 14 implementers. In the Table, for the sake of readability, the three main groups of functions have been referred to as “clinical”, “monitoring” and “social” respectively.

Partner short name	Health Information System	Excel	e-diabetes.si (Slovenia)	myDiabby	Moodle	Slack	Teams (including MS forms)	Facebook closed group (no private surveys)	Lifeseize (for webinars)	Academy NFZ (Poland)	Webropol survey
Sciensano (BE)				clinical; social; monitoring (under finalization with the Company)							
NIJZ (SI)			clinical; social; monitoring (under verification)								
MoH BG (BG)					clinical; social; monitoring (under verification)	clinical; social; monitoring (alternative to Moodle)					

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ALEXANDRA (EL)											
MoH SR (SK)											
FDA (FI)	clinical				social						monitoring
ISS (+AOUP, ASLROMA2, FPG) (IT)					clinical; social; monitoring						
DGS (PT)					clinical; social; monitoring (asked to ISS)						
NPHC (HU)											
NFZ (PL)		clinical			clinical; social; monitoring (asked to ISS)		social; monitoring (under decision; alternative to Moodle)	social; monitoring (alternative to previous ones)		social; monitoring (alternative to previous)	

CSPA/SESPA/ FICYT (ES)	clinical						social; monitoring				
SCS-IDIVAL (ES)	clinical										
SERGAS (ES)	clinical								social		
MIFH (MT)		clinical									

Finally, at the end of the T5.3 preparatory actions on the local digital solutions for the C4D online portals, a second, short survey was delivered to the implementers. The survey, simplified and with pre-defined multiple choices to answer, was administered via the same means as for the first survey, i.e. the document “T5.3 Template for Digital Platform fast feedback June 2023” was uploaded on Teams, activity was created on Click-Up, messages and emails were sent out, with the intention to add results to this document (proposed survey submission before July 10th 2023). At the time of this Deliverable finalization, submission was not completed yet. Thus, only the Survey questions are reported in Table 7. Available answers have been reported in Annex 6.2 without further analysis and comments.

Table 7 – Structured questions to collect updated information on C4D Digital Platform Implementation (June 2023).

#	Solution for	PLEASE PUT IN RED (AND COMPLETE IF NEEDED) THE MOST SUITABLE ANSWER					
1	CLINICAL DATA MANAGEMENT	LINK TO PATIENT'S ELECTRONIC HEALTH RECORD	DEDICATED SECTION, SEPARATE FROM MONITORING DATA AND SOCIAL INTERACTION SECTIONS	SAME PLATFORM AS FOR MONITORING DATA AND SOCIAL INTERACTION		OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
2	SELF-REPORTED MONITORING DATA WITH LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS	DEDICATED PLATFORM (PLEASE SPECIFY), WITH INTERNAL/LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS:	TEAMS OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER), WITH LINK TO SECURE INTERNAL SURVEYS	FACEBOOK CLOSED GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER), WITH LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS	WHATSAPP GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER), WITH LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS	OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
3	SELF-REPORTED MONITORING DATA WITH LINK TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS	DEDICATED PLATFORM LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	TEAMS OR SIMILAR, LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	FACEBOOK CLOSED GROUP OR SIMILAR, LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	WHATSAPP GROUP OR SIMILAR, LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS (REPORTED AT ITEM 2)
4	SOCIAL INTERACTION	DEDICATED PLATFORM (PLEASE SPECIFY):	TEAMS OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER)	FACEBOOK CLOSED GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER)	WHATSAPP GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER)		NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
5	GDPR COMPLIANCE (AND OTHER LOCAL LAWS IF IN FORCE)	PSEUDONYMISATION ALONE	PSEUDONYMISATION AND WRITTEN INFORMED CONSENT FOR PERSONAL DATA DISSEMINATION	WRITTEN INFORMED CONSENT FOR PERSONAL DATA DISSEMINATION		OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
6	DATA SECURITY	LOGIN BASED ON 2-LEVEL AUTHORIZATION	LOGIN BASED ON 1-LEVEL AUTHORIZATION			OTHER SOLUTIONS	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET

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						(PLEASE SPECIFY):	
7	DEVICES TO BE USED	PC, LAPTOP, TABLET	SMARTPHONE	PC, LAPTOP, TABLET AND SMARTPHONE		OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET

Those implementers who are planning to use a Moodle-based platform hosted by ISS were additionally asked to indicate contact persons for online training and future actions planning.

3.4. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR LOCAL DIGITAL SOLUTIONS

Recommendations on the use of the proposed applications and tools have been collected in Table 8, where main features, possible usage and risks are summarized for each mentioned application and for two additional applications.

Table 8 – Main features, possible usage and risks for applications and tools suggested by C4D implementers as possible solutions for the digital platform.

Name	Description	Proposed use	Data security issues
Health Information System	Local/Regional/National health information system managing clinical data (full compliance with GDPR and local laws)	clinical data	none
Excel	Microsoft spreadsheet. License cost: to be defined (not free of charge).	clinical data; monitoring data	Security measures: it is possible to block cells (formulas and/or content); it is possible to protect the spreadsheet by using passwords. Security Risk: there is no compliance with GDPR. Storage certainty only in case of Agreement with Microsoft. Additional risk in case of manual digitalization of clinical data from other sources. Pseudonymization may help (see section 3.4.1).

e-diabetes.si (Slovenia)	dedicated healthcare/educational platform. Compliant with GDPR. Costs: to be retrieved	clinical data; social interaction; data monitoring	not known; features under verification at NIJZ
myDiabby	dedicated healthcare diabetes-oriented platform (developer: MDHC SAS, Paris, France); Belgium site: https://www.mydiabby.be/ CE mark for MD, class I. Compliance with GDPR. Costs: variable; to be determined	clinical data; social interaction; data monitoring	Security issues: it seems that, unless differently (and formally) established, data are stored, managed and owned by the developer, also for research purposes. Adaptation under verification. Pseudonymization may help (see section 3.4.1).
Moodle	Open source learning management system. GDPR compliant. It needs to be installed on and managed by a safe (GDPR and local laws) IT infrastructure. It may use verified tools for social interaction (BBB) and data monitoring. Free of charge.	Social interaction and data monitoring (Finland, also integrated with Webropol survey). Clinical data, social interaction and data monitoring (Italy and Portugal, possibly Poland, Bulgaria, Spain and Malta)	Safe and compliant with GDPR, but its applications (“courses”) must be hosted by the reference IT infrastructure (server and cloud or databases). Pseudonymization may help (see section 3.4.1).
Slack	Digital Platform based on an advanced API and more than 2500 apps. Managed by the	Clinical data, social interaction and data	Safe and compliant with GDPR; different levels of

	Slack Fund, a venture capital fund. Owned by Slack Technologies LLC (USA), a Company within Salesforce. Worldwide disseminated structure. EU customers are managed by Slack Technologies Limited (Dublin, Ireland). Compliance with GDPR, IT standards (IEC 2700x series), main data security and privacy laws/requirements. Possibility to establish the location for data storage. Available through paid licences (free version has not enough features for C4D pilot implementation). Tools for C4D pilots' features to be checked.	monitoring (under study in Bulgaria, as an alternative to Moodle)	authentication; requires installation on host servers; location for data storage can be established. Pseudonymization may help (see section 3.4.1).
Teams (including Microsoft Forms)	Microsoft messaging application intended as a workspace for real-time/offline collaboration and communication, meetings, file and app sharing. Declared as GDPR compliant, full compliance depends on agreements on data storage and management. Available through paid licenses.	Social interaction and data monitoring (survey available through the tool MS Forms)	"Full safety" actually depend on the clear agreement which can be signed with MS. Pseudonymization may not be possible (see section 3.4.1).
Facebook hidden and private group (no private surveys)	Internet social network (owner: Meta Inc, U.S.). Declared as not fully compliant with GDPR. Data storage and use unknown/uncontrollable. Facebook closed and hidden groups guarantee that data sharing only occur among group participants (other Facebook	Social interaction (under verification).	Lack of compliance with GDPR. Possibly usable for social interaction (in closed hidden groups) if the user signs the informed consent. Data monitoring possibly performed through links to

	<p>users cannot see and access them).</p> <p>Data from surveys within a closed hidden group are shared among all the group participants.</p> <p>Free of charge.</p>		<p>external survey tools (Facebook surveys are not private).</p> <p>Pseudonymization may help (see section 3.4.1).</p>
Lifeseize (for webinars)	<p>Communication and workplace collaboration platform (owner: Lifeseize Inc, U.S.). Roughly declared as partial GDPR compliance (without the possibility to verify). Data storage and use unknown/uncontrollable.</p> <p>Team (closed?) groups are available (as in Facebook).</p> <p>Costs: to be determined</p>	Social interaction (under verification in Spain (SERGAS)).	Lack of compliance with GDPR. Possibly usable for social interaction (in closed hidden groups) if the user signs the informed consent. Data monitoring possibly performed through links to external survey tools.
Academy NFZ (Poland)	<p>dedicated (University?) educational platform. GDPR compliant (to be verified with Partner). Tools for social interaction and data monitoring under exploration.</p> <p>Costs: to be determined.</p>	Social interaction and data monitoring (under verification)	not known; features under verification at NFZ
Webropol survey	<p>Web tool for creating surveys; only available in cloud (owner: Webropol Oy, Helsinki, Finland). The owner becomes data owner. GDPR compliant.</p> <p>Cost of licenses: to be determined.</p>	Data monitoring	Other security issues not known. The Webropol owner becomes data owner (this shall be clarified to Ethical Committee): pseudonymization may help (see section 3.4.1).

Limesurvey	<p>Web tool for creating surveys. GDPR compliant. Resident installation on payment or free of charge, with data stored and managed on local (user proprietary) server. Cloud license with possibility to establish the location for data storage).</p> <p>Suggested by ISS (i.e. not proposed by C4D implementers)</p>	Data monitoring	Other security issues: not known.
Google survey	<p>Web tool for creating surveys. Declared as only partially compliant with GDPR. Data storage and use unknown/uncontrollable.</p> <p>Mentioned by ISS as a risky solution requiring special attention</p>	Data monitoring	Lack of compliance with GDPR. In case of use, pseudonymization is “mandatory” (see section 3.4.1).
Whatsapp (or similar tools)	<p>Mobile and web app for social network activities.</p> <p>Owned by Meta (different owners for other, similar products).</p> <p>Data and contents are owned and used by Meta.</p> <p>Free of charge.</p>	Suggested by some implementers to be used for social interaction activities and for communicating links to monitoring data tools	<p>Several risks to keep in mind, among which: Whatsapp surveys are public in the group; Whatsapp contents can never be checked for approval before publication; Whatsapp contents can be always shared outside the group.</p> <p>Lack of compliance with GDPR. In case of use, pseudonymization is “mandatory” (see section 3.4.1).</p>

2.1.1. Pseudonymization and informed consent

Pseudonymization is defined as a recommended procedure to ensure that personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that this additional information is kept separately and subject to technical and organizational security measures.

Whenever possible, it is recommended that all clinical and personal data collected and managed through a C4D digital platform are protected by pseudonymised them, i.e. by removing the association between the data and any personal detail which may render them clearly associated with the specific participant.

The basic steps of a pseudonymisation procedure might be done as follows:

- the clinical premises where participants are enrolled creates, updates and securely stores an association table containing the correspondence between participants and assigned codes;
- one or more individuals at the clinical premises shall be in charge for the above responsibility (official appointment by the data protection officer);
- the assigned codes shall be totally anonymous, i.e. they cannot refer to identifiable individual data as for example the birthdate

This procedure has been discussed and agreed among the Italian pilot implementers. Additionally, the pseudonymization requirement is asked mandatorily by ISS to those implementers who will prefer to have their C4D portal hosted by ISS IT service and system.

Please note that the above procedure only refers to the pseudonymization of collected data. For a full pseudonymization of a participant, also his/her registration details (including the email account) should be not attributable to the participants. In this case, simple suggestions to reach the goals might be: to register the participant without the family name (for example by replacing it with the pseudonymization code); to use a non-attributable email account (i.e. not clearly containing the participant's family name), if existing, or, whenever possible, to purposely create a new account. Interesting to know, a complete "anonymous" email account can be created, for example through the provider Tutanota (<https://mail.tutanota.com/login>): the new account can be created free of charge without delivering personal data to the provider. This solution, however, might not be straight accepted by some applications, like Facebook, where the identity of each profile is required.

Whichever the level of data security will be setup and guaranteed for data managed through the C4D digital platform, it will be however mandatory to acquire and securely store the signed informed consent by all users of the platform, independently of the role.

2.1.3. Preliminary recommendations for C4D digital platform contents

Despite C4D portal's contents are still under preparation, some aspects have already been addressed because they also impact on the adoption of digital solutions. In particular, the critical issue has been addressed of the usage, adaptation and possible dissemination of VL materials. Several animations, slides, videos and documents have been shared, in fact, by VL with the C4D Consortium. On the basis of the C4D Grant Agreement, those materials can be used in the C4D pilots; however, rules shall be strictly respected in terms of VL copyright, acknowledgments and so on.

All implementers shall refer to the project document "C4D_Rules dissemination and communication" (available in the C4D Teams repository).

3.5. FEASIBILITY OF THE ISS DIGITAL SOLUTION

At the project start, on February 1st 2023, the decision had already been taken at ISS to develop a Moodle-based web application. Moodle is an open-source learning management system, free of charge, GDPR compliant. ISS, and the C4D ISS team in particular, has long experience in developing and managing Moodle-based distance learning modules. One of the IT experts in the C4D ISS team (Daniele Cordella) is a valuable and acknowledged Moodle software developer (<https://moodle.org/dev/>) who had previously developed a survey module (the validated SurveyPro tool) which immediately appeared as a suitable and secure means to collect participants' data and feedback. Besides the usual tools for distance learning, a Moodle-based digital solution may also exploit additional, verified tools for social interaction (as for example the Big Blue Button (BBB) tool for videocalls) and data monitoring. To properly run Moodle-based platforms, a Moodle instance needs to be installed on and managed by a secure - GDPR and local laws compliant - IT environment, requirement which is fully satisfied by the ISS IT infrastructure.

A graphical summary of the ISS digital solution is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – Graphical representation of the ISS, Moodle-based digital solution

Following the characterization of the VL platform, only two features were not retrieved among the available Moodle tools namely i) a suitable management of the participant's agenda to schedule assignments, activities, or events, and ii) the plot of self-reported monitoring data. The former issue was addressed by adopting a more suitable validated theme than the default one (Theme Moove for Moodle 3.8) for the platform interface and to slightly adapt the software; the latter required some additional software coding. All software adaptations were verified and released according to the Moodle development and ISS procedures.

Bench and feasibility tests at ISS showed the secure implementation of the C4D expected features. Discussion with the Italian implementers gave positive feedback as well; one more useful feature was suggested by the health professionals, which is currently under investigation, to allow the participants to easily take and upload images or short videos from a computer-connected webcam. Tools are currently under finalization as for the assignment of the peculiar access conditions, availability check, uploading of preliminary contents, user manuals delivery. At the end of this phase, hopefully by the end of July, the Italian health professionals will be registered to log in, surf and test the platform. Following this feedback and an expected refinement step, the digital platform will be ready for use.

To summarize, the consolidated ISS C4D online portal will address all the requirements listed in Table 3 and will be delivered in Italian.

Due to the Moodle multi-language features, the framework of the portal (not the contents, responsibility of each project participant) can be easily translated in other languages. Further, replicating and hosting few additional portals for other Countries participating to the C4D pilot studies may be affordable for ISS IT services and personnel. For this reason, support has been offered to those implementers who haven't enough resources to develop or setup a suitable digital solution in time for the pilot programmes administration. Main terms and requirements to deliver and host a portal for a C4D non-Italian implementer have been illustrated during the dedicated online meeting (June 2023) by showing the Figure 2 summary.

Figure 2 – ISS support to other implementing Partners – terms and requirements

Additional email exchanging and online meetings for deeper explanations are currently ongoing on demand.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Within the C4D Joint Action, the online portal represents a crucial means to deliver, at Country level, adapted programmes inspired to the Best Practice “ReverseDiabetes2Now” (Voeding Leeft, The Netherlands). The Best Practice, which addresses the improvement of lifestyle and therapy management of patients with type 2 Diabetes and overweight or obesity, mainly relies, in fact, on both in-presence and online programmes. Through the platform, a multi-disciplinary, trained team of health professionals is meant to digitally interact with the participants and to manage clinical and self-reported data, and social interaction. The digital platforms within the C4D, though with reasonably less maturity, should resemble the approach and the tools of the VL platform, to help investigating transferability, feasibility and sustainability of the Best Practice.

Preparatory activities in Task 5.3, led by ISS and conducted in synergy with the whole Consortium, especially with pilot implementers, and also supported by the VL team, started before the official beginning of the project and are still ongoing. Main outcomes of those activities were: the characterization of the VL platform; the identification of key-elements of a C4D online portal; the identification of local digital solutions, reached through an iterative process based on resources analysis and needs and requirements detection; recommendations and support to have all pilot implementers ready on time for the execution of all the pilots.

While the topic of the digital platform implementation might have been slightly underestimated at the proposal preparation stage, the methodology used in T5.3 and the information produced will hopefully help all pilot implementers to reach the proper awareness and the means to cope with this relevant issue.

The ISS digital platform, based on the Moodle, open-source learning management system, may represent an inspiring solution. As an “all-in-one” platform, it addresses all the features of the VL platform and allows the management of: participants’ clinical data; participants’ self-reported data (monitoring functions); activities, resources, and community-based interactions among the participants and with the multidisciplinary team’s members (social interaction).

Simpler and faster solutions are also discussed in the present document, highlighting advantages and security risks; they might be especially useful in those cases where a provisional portal is preferred/affordable at this stage of the project.

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Annex 6.3 contains an additional support to implementers for better scheduling the actions to prepare and manage the digital platform.

The impact of digital platforms not available or not fully performing at the start of the C4D pilot programmes might be quite heavy for the successful implementation of the programmes. All the actions taken, as reported in this Deliverable, should mitigate this risk. Among the actions, worth mentioning is the hosting of other Countries' pilots on the Italian, ISS IT infrastructure, as a temporary solution to be replaced either during the pilots or soon after the end of the Joint Action.

While the present document is focussed on the framework of the digital platforms, their contents, out of the scope of the document itself, are still at a developing stage and were not commented hereby.

5. REFERENCES

EU General Data Protection Regulation GDPR 2016/679. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/IT/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32016R0679>

Information and materials for C4D pilots' implementers:
<https://ficyt.sharepoint.com/sites/Care4Diabetes-Pilots/>

Website of the Best Practice ReverseDiabetes2Now: <https://reverseddiabetes2now.com/>

Moodle open-source development environment: <https://moodle.org>

Webropol data policy: <https://webropol.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/Webropols-Privacy-Statement.pdf>

LimeSurvey_{GmbH} data policy: <https://www.limesurvey.org/support/faq/39-data-protection-and-policy/515-where-and-how-is-my-survey-data-hosted-stored>

Lifesize data policy: <https://www.lifesize.com/security-privacy-and-compliance/>

Meta data policy: <https://www.facebook.com/business/gdpr>

Tutanota data policy and provider description: <https://mail.tutanota.com>

ENISA – Pseudonymisation techniques and best practices:
<https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/pseudonymisation-techniques-and-best-practices>

6. ANNEXES

6.1 LIST OF C4D PILOT IMPLEMENTERS

#	Country	Area/site	Implementer
1	Belgium	Wallonia	Sciensano [40 pts (20+20); hybrid]
2	Bulgaria	Blagoevgrad	RHI (supporting entity), supported and coordinated by MoH BG [40 pts (20+20); hybrid]
3	Finland	Country level possibly	FDA (AE), under the coordination of THL [40 pts (20+20); fully online]
4	Greece	Attica (incl. Athens)	ALEXANDRA, under the coordination of 1st YPE ATTICA [60 pts (20+40); hybrid]
5	Hungary	Central Hungary	NPHC [40 pts (20+20); hybrid]
6	Italy	Lazio Region and Tuscany Region	ASL ROMA 2, FPG, AOUP, under the coordination of ISS (CA) [60 pts (20+40); hybrid]
7	Malta	Country level	MFH [40 pts (20+20); fully physical]
8	Poland	Mazovian district	NFZ and WMU [40 pts (20+20); hybrid]
9	Portugal	Lisbon & Tagus Valley Region and Alentejo Region	DGS and APDP [60 pts (20+40); hybrid]
10	Slovakia	Country level possibly	MoH SR supported by externally concreted patients' organisations (see budget) [40 pts (20+20); hybrid]
11	Slovenia	South-East Region	SB-NM, under coordination of NIJZ [40 pts (20+20); hybrid]
12	Spain	Asturias, Cantabria, Galicia, Andalucía, Extremadura,	CSPA-SESPA, SCS-IDIVAL, SERGAS, SAS-FPS, JUNTAEX,

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		Aragón	GAIAP [360 pts (120+240); hybrid]
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(pts: patients)

6.2 UPDATE ON C4D DIGITAL SOLUTIONS – PROVISIONAL RESULTS (JUNE 2023)

Nine fast survey answered tables are reported here below in their temporal uploading sequence, new page for each table.

Partner short name: JUNTAEX

#	SOLUTION FOR:	PLEASE PUT IN RED (AND COMPLETE IF NEEDED) THE MOST SUITABLE ANSWER					
1	CLINICAL DATA MANAGEMENT	LINK TO PATIENT'S ELECTRONIC HEALTH RECORD	DEDICATED SECTION, SEPARATE FROM MONITORING DATA AND SOCIAL INTERACTION SECTIONS	SAME PLATFORM AS FOR MONITORING DATA AND SOCIAL INTERACTION		OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
2	SELF-REPORTED MONITORING DATA WITH <u>LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS</u>	DEDICATED PLATFORM (PLEASE SPECIFY), WITH INTERNAL/LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS:	TEAMS OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER), WITH LINK TO SECURE INTERNAL SURVEYS	FACEBOOK CLOSED GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER), WITH LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS	WHATSAPP GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER), WITH LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS	OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
3	SELF-REPORTED MONITORING DATA WITH <u>LINK TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS</u>	DEDICATED PLATFORM LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	TEAMS OR SIMILAR, LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	FACEBOOK CLOSED GROUP OR SIMILAR, LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	WHATSAPP GROUP OR SIMILAR, LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS (REPORTED AT ITEM 2)
4	SOCIAL INTERACTION	DEDICATED PLATFORM (PLEASE SPECIFY):	TEAMS OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER)	FACEBOOK CLOSED GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER)	WHATSAPP GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER)		NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
5	GDPR COMPLIANCE (AND OTHER LOCAL LAWS IF IN FORCE)	PSEUDONYMISATION ALONE	PSEUDONYMISATION AND WRITTEN INFORMED CONSENT FOR PERSONAL DATA DISSEMINATION	WRITTEN INFORMED CONSENT FOR PERSONAL DATA DISSEMINATION		OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
6	DATA SECURITY	LOGIN BASED ON 2-LEVEL AUTHORIZATION	LOGIN BASED ON 1-LEVEL AUTHORIZATION			OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET

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7	DEVICES TO BE USED	PC, LAPTOP, TABLET	SMARTPHONE	PC, LAPTOP, TABLET AND SMARTPHONE		OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
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If you are planning to use a moodle-based platform hosted by ISS, please indicate contact person/persons for online training: We don't know yet but if so, the person will be XXX (masked by ISS)

Any additional comment or detail: This is our current situation that can be modified in the coming months if necessary

Partner short name: NFZ

#	SOLUTION FOR:	PLEASE PUT IN RED (AND COMPLETE IF NEEDED) THE MOST SUITABLE ANSWER					
1	CLINICAL DATA MANAGEMENT	LINK TO PATIENT'S ELECTRONIC HEALTH RECORD	DEDICATED SECTION, SEPARATE FROM MONITORING DATA AND SOCIAL INTERACTION SECTIONS	SAME PLATFORM AS FOR MONITORING DATA AND SOCIAL INTERACTION		OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY): PLANNING TO USE A MOODLE-BASED PLATFORM HOSTED BY ISS	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
2	SELF-REPORTED MONITORING DATA WITH <u>LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS</u>	DEDICATED PLATFORM (PLEASE SPECIFY), WITH INTERNAL/LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS:	TEAMS OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER), WITH LINK TO SECURE INTERNAL SURVEYS	FACEBOOK CLOSED GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER), WITH LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS	WHATSAPP GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER), WITH LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS	OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY): PLANNING TO USE A MOODLE-BASED PLATFORM HOSTED BY ISS	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
3	SELF-REPORTED MONITORING DATA WITH <u>LINK TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS</u>	DEDICATED PLATFORM LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	TEAMS OR SIMILAR, LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	FACEBOOK CLOSED GROUP OR SIMILAR, LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	WHATSAPP GROUP OR SIMILAR, LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY): PLANNING TO USE A MOODLE-BASED PLATFORM HOSTED BY ISS	LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS (REPORTED AT ITEM 2)
4	SOCIAL INTERACTION	DEDICATED PLATFORM (PLEASE SPECIFY):	TEAMS OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER)	FACEBOOK CLOSED GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER)	WHATSAPP GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER)	OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY): PLANNING TO USE A MOODLE-BASED PLATFORM HOSTED BY ISS	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
5	GDPR COMPLIANCE (AND OTHER LOCAL LAWS IF IN FORCE)	PSEUDONYMISATION ALONE	PSEUDONYMISATION AND WRITTEN INFORMED CONSENT	WRITTEN INFORMED CONSENT FOR		OTHER SOLUTIONS	NO SOLUTION

			FOR PERSONAL DATA DISSEMINATION	PERSONAL DATA DISSEMINATION		(PLEASE SPECIFY):	IDENTIFIED YET
6	DATA SECURITY	LOGIN BASED ON 2- LEVEL AUTHORIZATION	LOGIN BASED ON 1- LEVEL AUTHORIZATION			OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY): PLANNING TO USE A MOODLE- BASED PLATFORM HOSTED BY ISS	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
7	DEVICES TO BE USED	PC, LAPTOP, TABLET	SMARTPHONE	PC, LAPTOP, TABLET AND SMARTPHONE		OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET

If you are planning to use a moodle-based platform hosted by ISS, please indicate contact person/persons for online training: xxx (two persons, names masked by ISS)

Partner short name: SERGAS

#	SOLUTION FOR:	PLEASE PUT IN RED (AND COMPLETE IF NEEDED) THE MOST SUITABLE ANSWER					
1	CLINICAL DATA MANAGEMENT	LINK TO PATIENT'S ELECTRONIC HEALTH RECORD	DEDICATED SECTION, SEPARATE FROM MONITORING DATA AND SOCIAL INTERACTION SECTIONS	SAME PLATFORM AS FOR MONITORING DATA AND SOCIAL INTERACTION, BUT WITH DIFFERENT DEGREE OF PROTECTION AND DEFINED ACCESSIBILITY		OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
2	SELF-REPORTED MONITORING DATA WITH <u>LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS</u>	DEDICATED PLATFORM (PLEASE SPECIFY), WITH INTERNAL/LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS: UNDER CONSTRUCTION	TEAMS OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER), WITH LINK TO SECURE INTERNAL SURVEYS	FACEBOOK CLOSED GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER), WITH LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS	WHATSAPP GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER), WITH LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS	OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
3	SELF-REPORTED MONITORING DATA WITH <u>LINK TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS</u>	DEDICATED PLATFORM LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	TEAMS OR SIMILAR, LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	FACEBOOK CLOSED GROUP OR SIMILAR, LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	WHATSAPP GROUP OR SIMILAR, LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS (REPORTED AT ITEM 2)
4	SOCIAL INTERACTION	DEDICATED PLATFORM (PLEASE SPECIFY):	TEAMS OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER)	FACEBOOK CLOSED GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER)	WHATSAPP GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER)		NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
5	GDPR COMPLIANCE (AND OTHER LOCAL LAWS IF IN FORCE)	PSEUDONYMISATION ALONE	PSEUDONYMISATION AND WRITTEN INFORMED CONSENT FOR PERSONAL DATA DISSEMINATION AND ALL ACTIONS RELATED TO THE DATA COLLECTION AND MANAGEMENT WITHIN C4D	WRITTEN INFORMED CONSENT FOR PERSONAL DATA DISSEMINATION		OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
6	DATA SECURITY	LOGIN BASED ON 2-LEVEL AUTHORIZATION	LOGIN BASED ON 1-LEVEL AUTHORIZATION			OTHER SOLUTIONS	NO SOLUTION

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						(PLEASE SPECIFY):	IDENTIFIED YET
7	DEVICES TO BE USED	PC, LAPTOP, TABLET	SMARTPHONE	PC, LAPTOP, TABLET AND SMARTPHONE		OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET

Partner short name: Sciensano

#	SOLUTION FOR:	PLEASE PUT IN RED (AND COMPLETE IF NEEDED) THE MOST SUITABLE ANSWER					
1	CLINICAL DATA MANAGEMENT	LINK TO PATIENT'S ELECTRONIC HEALTH RECORD	DEDICATED SECTION, SEPARATE FROM MONITORING DATA AND SOCIAL INTERACTION SECTIONS	SAME PLATFORM AS FOR MONITORING DATA AND SOCIAL INTERACTION		OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY): CLINICAL DATA WILL NOT BE MANAGED THROUGH A PLATFORM. PSEUDO ANONYMIZED CLINICAL DATA WILL BE COMPLETED VIA REDCAP, LOCATED ON THE SCIENSANO SERVER, AS CASE REPORT FORM BY THE NURSES OR THE PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR. SOCIAL INTERACTION WILL TAKE PLACE ON A PRIVATE FACEBOOK GROUP INDEPENDENTLY OF THE CLINICAL DATA.	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
2	SELF-REPORTED MONITORING DATA WITH <u>LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS</u>	DEDICATED PLATFORM (PLEASE SPECIFY), WITH INTERNAL/LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS:	TEAMS OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER), WITH LINK TO SECURE INTERNAL SURVEYS	FACEBOOK CLOSED GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER), WITH LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS	WHATSAPP GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER), WITH LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS	OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY): SELF-REPORTED MONITORING DATA WILL BE COMPLETED VIA A REDCAP SECURE SURVEY LINK SENT BY THE LOCAL COORDINATOR TO PARTICIPANTS' EMAIL ADDRESS.	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
3	SELF-REPORTED MONITORING DATA WITH <u>LINK TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS</u>	DEDICATED PLATFORM LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	TEAMS OR SIMILAR, LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	FACEBOOK CLOSED GROUP OR SIMILAR, LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	WHATSAPP GROUP OR SIMILAR, LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY): NOT APPLICABLE	LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS (REPORTED AT ITEM 2)
4	SOCIAL INTERACTION	DEDICATED PLATFORM (PLEASE SPECIFY):	TEAMS OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER)	FACEBOOK CLOSED GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER)	WHATSAPP GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER)	IN ADDITION, A WHATSAPP GROUP WILL BE CREATED HOWEVER, AS CONTENT ON WHATSAPP CANNOT BE MODERATED BY THE ADMIN, ONLY THE ADMIN, I.E. THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY HEALTHCARE TEAM, WILL BE ABLE TO SEND MESSAGES THROUGH THIS CHANNEL (UNIDIRECTIONAL)	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET

						CHANNEL). THE PURPOSE OF UNIDIRECTIONAL WHATSAPP MESSAGES WILL BE TO INCREASE TRAFFIC ON THE FACEBOOK PAGE AND ENSURE CONTENT VISIBILITY AND WILL ONLY SERVE TO NOTIFY PARTICIPANTS THAT NEW CONTENT HAS BEEN PUBLISHED ON THE FACEBOOK PAGE AND SEND REMINDERS (GLUCOSE SELF-MONITORING, PARTICIPATION DAYS, FILLING IN QUESTIONNAIRES).	
5	GDPR COMPLIANCE (AND OTHER LOCAL LAWS IF IN FORCE)	PSEUDONYMISATION ALONE	PSEUDONYMISATION AND WRITTEN INFORMED CONSENT FOR PERSONAL DATA DISSEMINATION	WRITTEN INFORMED CONSENT FOR PERSONAL DATA DISSEMINATION		OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
6	DATA SECURITY	LOGIN BASED ON 2-LEVEL AUTHORIZATION	LOGIN BASED ON 1-LEVEL AUTHORIZATION			OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY): IDENTIFIABLE DATA WILL BE STORED ON THE LOCAL HEALTH FACILITY SERVER WHILE CLINICAL DATA WILL BE STORED ON THE SCIENSANO SERVER TO AVOID HAVING IDENTIFIABLE AND CLINICAL DATA ON THE SAME SERVER.	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
7	DEVICES TO BE USED	PC, LAPTOP, TABLET	SMARTPHONE	PC, LAPTOP, TABLET AND SMARTPHONE		OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET

Partner short name: ISS + AOUP + ASLROMA2 + FPG

#	SOLUTION FOR:	PLEASE PUT IN RED (AND COMPLETE IF NEEDED) THE MOST SUITABLE ANSWER					
1	CLINICAL DATA MANAGEMENT	LINK TO PATIENT'S ELECTRONIC HEALTH RECORD	DEDICATED SECTION, SEPARATE FROM MONITORING DATA AND SOCIAL INTERACTION SECTIONS	SAME PLATFORM AS FOR MONITORING DATA AND SOCIAL INTERACTION		OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
2	SELF-REPORTED MONITORING DATA WITH <u>LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS</u>	DEDICATED PLATFORM (PLEASE SPECIFY), WITH INTERNAL LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS: MOODLE-BASED ISS PLATFORM, USING SURVEYPRO SURVEYS (VERIFIED MOODLE SECURE TOOL)	TEAMS OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER), WITH LINK TO SECURE INTERNAL SURVEYS	FACEBOOK CLOSED GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER), WITH LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS	WHATSAPP GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER), WITH LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS	OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
3	SELF-REPORTED MONITORING DATA WITH <u>LINK TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS</u>	DEDICATED PLATFORM LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	TEAMS OR SIMILAR, LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	FACEBOOK CLOSED GROUP OR SIMILAR, LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	WHATSAPP GROUP OR SIMILAR, LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY): NOT APPLICABLE	LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS (REPORTED AT ITEM 2)
4	SOCIAL INTERACTION	DEDICATED PLATFORM (PLEASE SPECIFY): MOODLE-BASED ISS PLATFORM	TEAMS OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER)	FACEBOOK CLOSED GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER)	WHATSAPP GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER)		NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
5	GDPR COMPLIANCE (AND OTHER LOCAL LAWS IF IN FORCE)	PSEUDONYMISATION ALONE	PSEUDONYMISATION AND WRITTEN INFORMED CONSENT FOR PERSONAL DATA DISSEMINATION	WRITTEN INFORMED CONSENT FOR PERSONAL DATA DISSEMINATION		OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
6	DATA SECURITY	LOGIN BASED ON 2-LEVEL AUTHORIZATION	LOGIN BASED ON 1-LEVEL AUTHORIZATION			OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
7	DEVICES TO BE USED	PC, LAPTOP, TABLET	SMARTPHONE	PC, LAPTOP, TABLET AND SMARTPHONE		OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET

Partner short name: NIJZ (answers reported elsewhere, table adapted by ISS)

#	SOLUTION FOR:	PLEASE PUT IN RED (AND COMPLETE IF NEEDED) THE MOST SUITABLE ANSWER					
1	CLINICAL DATA MANAGEMENT	LINK TO PATIENT'S ELECTRONIC HEALTH RECORD	DEDICATED SECTION, SEPARATE FROM MONITORING DATA AND SOCIAL INTERACTION SECTIONS	SAME PLATFORM AS FOR MONITORING DATA AND SOCIAL INTERACTION		OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
2	SELF-REPORTED MONITORING DATA WITH <u>LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS</u>	DEDICATED PLATFORM (PLEASE SPECIFY), WITH INTERNAL/LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS: EXISTING PLATFORM (E-DIABETES-SI), WHICH WILL BE UPGRADED TO ASSURE THE SECURITY NEEDED IN LINE WITH GDPR AND SLOVENIAN LAW ON DATA PROTECTION.	TEAMS OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER), WITH LINK TO SECURE INTERNAL SURVEYS	FACEBOOK CLOSED GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER), WITH LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS	WHATSAPP GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER), WITH LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS	OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
3	SELF-REPORTED MONITORING DATA WITH <u>LINK TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS</u>	DEDICATED PLATFORM LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	TEAMS OR SIMILAR, LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	FACEBOOK CLOSED GROUP OR SIMILAR, LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	WHATSAPP GROUP OR SIMILAR, LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY): NOT APPLICABLE	LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS (REPORTED AT ITEM 2)
4	SOCIAL INTERACTION	DEDICATED PLATFORM (PLEASE SPECIFY): EXISTING PLATFORM (E-DIABETES-SI), WHICH WILL BE UPGRADED TO ASSURE THE SECURITY NEEDED IN LINE WITH GDPR AND SLOVENIAN LAW ON DATA PROTECTION.	TEAMS OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER)	FACEBOOK CLOSED GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER)	WHATSAPP GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER)		NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
5	GDPR COMPLIANCE (AND OTHER LOCAL LAWS IF IN FORCE)	PSEUDONYMISATION ALONE	PSEUDONYMISATION AND WRITTEN INFORMED CONSENT FOR PERSONAL DATA DISSEMINATION	WRITTEN INFORMED CONSENT FOR PERSONAL DATA DISSEMINATION		OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET

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6	DATA SECURITY	LOGIN BASED ON 2- LEVEL AUTHORIZATION	LOGIN BASED ON 1- LEVEL AUTHORIZATION			OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
7	DEVICES TO BE USED	PC, LAPTOP, TABLET	SMARTPHONE	PC, LAPTOP, TABLET AND SMARTPHONE		OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET

Partner short name: CSPA-FICYT-SESPA

#	SOLUTION FOR:	PLEASE PUT IN RED (AND COMPLETE IF NEEDED) THE MOST SUITABLE ANSWER					
1	CLINICAL DATA MANAGEMENT	LINK TO PATIENT'S ELECTRONIC HEALTH RECORD	DEDICATED SECTION, SEPARATE FROM MONITORING DATA AND SOCIAL INTERACTION SECTIONS	SAME PLATFORM AS FOR MONITORING DATA AND SOCIAL INTERACTION		OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
2	SELF-REPORTED MONITORING DATA WITH <u>LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS</u>	DEDICATED PLATFORM (PLEASE SPECIFY), WITH INTERNAL/LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS: MOODLE-BASED PLATFORM HOSTED BY ISS	TEAMS OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER), WITH LINK TO SECURE INTERNAL SURVEYS	FACEBOOK CLOSED GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER), WITH LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS	WHATSAPP GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER), WITH LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS	OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY): MOODLE-BASED PLATFORM HOSTED BY ISS	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
3	SELF-REPORTED MONITORING DATA WITH <u>LINK TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS</u>	DEDICATED PLATFORM LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY): MOODLE-BASED PLATFORM HOSTED BY ISS	TEAMS OR SIMILAR, LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	FACEBOOK CLOSED GROUP OR SIMILAR, LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	WHATSAPP GROUP OR SIMILAR, LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY): N/A	LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS (REPORTED AT ITEM 2)
4	SOCIAL INTERACTION	DEDICATED PLATFORM (PLEASE SPECIFY):	TEAMS OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER)	FACEBOOK CLOSED GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER)	WHATSAPP GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER)	MOODLE-BASED PLATFORM HOSTED BY ISS	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
5	GDPR COMPLIANCE (AND OTHER LOCAL LAWS IF IN FORCE)	PSEUDONYMISATION ALONE	PSEUDONYMISATION AND WRITTEN INFORMED CONSENT FOR PERSONAL DATA DISSEMINATION	WRITTEN INFORMED CONSENT FOR PERSONAL DATA DISSEMINATION		OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY): AGGREGATED ANONYMISED DATA	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
6	DATA SECURITY	LOGIN BASED ON 2-LEVEL AUTHORIZATION	LOGIN BASED ON 1-LEVEL AUTHORIZATION			OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
7	DEVICES TO BE USED	PC, LAPTOP, TABLET	SMARTPHONE	PC, LAPTOP, TABLET AND SMARTPHONE		OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET

If you are planning to use a moodle-based platform hosted by ISS, please indicate contact person/persons for online training: xxx (one person indicated, name masked by ISS)

Partner short name: MFH (Malta)

#	SOLUTION FOR:	PLEASE PUT IN RED (AND COMPLETE IF NEEDED) THE MOST SUITABLE ANSWER					
1	CLINICAL DATA MANAGEMENT	LINK TO PATIENT'S ELECTRONIC HEALTH RECORD	DEDICATED SECTION, SEPARATE FROM MONITORING DATA AND SOCIAL INTERACTION SECTIONS	SAME PLATFORM AS FOR MONITORING DATA AND SOCIAL INTERACTION		OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
2	SELF-REPORTED MONITORING DATA WITH <u>LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS</u>	DEDICATED PLATFORM (PLEASE SPECIFY), WITH INTERNAL/LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS:	TEAMS OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER), WITH LINK TO SECURE INTERNAL SURVEYS	FACEBOOK CLOSED GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER), WITH LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS	WHATSAPP GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER), WITH LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS	OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
3	SELF-REPORTED MONITORING DATA WITH <u>LINK TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS</u>	DEDICATED PLATFORM LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	TEAMS OR SIMILAR, LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	FACEBOOK CLOSED GROUP OR SIMILAR, LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	WHATSAPP GROUP OR SIMILAR, LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS (REPORTED AT ITEM 2)
4	SOCIAL INTERACTION	DEDICATED PLATFORM (PLEASE SPECIFY):	TEAMS OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER)	FACEBOOK CLOSED GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER)	WHATSAPP GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER)		NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
5	GDPR COMPLIANCE (AND OTHER LOCAL LAWS IF IN FORCE)	PSEUDONYMISATION ALONE	PSEUDONYMISATION AND WRITTEN INFORMED CONSENT FOR PERSONAL DATA DISSEMINATION	WRITTEN INFORMED CONSENT FOR PERSONAL DATA DISSEMINATION		OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
6	DATA SECURITY	LOGIN BASED ON 2-LEVEL AUTHORIZATION	LOGIN BASED ON 1-LEVEL AUTHORIZATION			OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
7	DEVICES TO BE USED	PC, LAPTOP, TABLET	SMARTPHONE	PC, LAPTOP, TABLET AND SMARTPHONE		OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET

If you are planning to use a moodle-based platform hosted by ISS, please indicate contact person/persons for online training: xxx (three persons indicated, names masked by ISS)

Partner short name: MoH-BG

#	SOLUTION FOR:	PLEASE PUT IN RED (AND COMPLETE IF NEEDED) THE MOST SUITABLE ANSWER					
1	CLINICAL DATA MANAGEMENT	LINK TO PATIENT'S ELECTRONIC HEALTH RECORD	DEDICATED SECTION, SEPARATE FROM MONITORING DATA AND SOCIAL INTERACTION SECTIONS	SAME PLATFORM AS FOR MONITORING DATA AND SOCIAL INTERACTION		OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
2	SELF-REPORTED MONITORING DATA WITH <u>LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS</u>	DEDICATED PLATFORM (PLEASE SPECIFY), WITH INTERNAL/LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS: MOODLE-BASED PLATFORM HOSTED BY ISS	TEAMS OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER), WITH LINK TO SECURE INTERNAL SURVEYS	FACEBOOK CLOSED GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER), WITH LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS	WHATSAPP GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER), WITH LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS	OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY): MOODLE-BASED PLATFORM HOSTED BY ISS	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
3	SELF-REPORTED MONITORING DATA WITH <u>LINK TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS</u>	DEDICATED PLATFORM LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY): MOODLE-BASED PLATFORM HOSTED BY ISS	TEAMS OR SIMILAR, LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	FACEBOOK CLOSED GROUP OR SIMILAR, LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	WHATSAPP GROUP OR SIMILAR, LINKED TO NON-SECURE SURVEYS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY): N/A	LINK TO SECURE SURVEYS (REPORTED AT ITEM 2)
4	SOCIAL INTERACTION	DEDICATED PLATFORM (PLEASE SPECIFY):	TEAMS OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER)	FACEBOOK CLOSED GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER)	WHATSAPP GROUP OR SIMILAR (SPECIFY IF OTHER)	MOODLE-BASED PLATFORM HOSTED BY ISS	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
5	GDPR COMPLIANCE (AND OTHER LOCAL LAWS IF IN FORCE)	PSEUDONYMISATION ALONE	PSEUDONYMISATION AND WRITTEN INFORMED CONSENT FOR PERSONAL DATA DISSEMINATION	WRITTEN INFORMED CONSENT FOR PERSONAL DATA DISSEMINATION		OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
6	DATA SECURITY	LOGIN BASED ON 2-LEVEL AUTHORIZATION	LOGIN BASED ON 1-LEVEL AUTHORIZATION			OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET
7	DEVICES TO BE USED	PC, LAPTOP, TABLET	SMARTPHONE	PC, LAPTOP, TABLET AND SMARTPHONE		OTHER SOLUTIONS (PLEASE SPECIFY):	NO SOLUTION IDENTIFIED YET

If you are planning to use a moodle-based platform hosted by ISS, please indicate contact person/persons for online training: xxx (one person indicated, name masked by ISS)

6.3 C4D PILOT IMPLEMENTATION PLAN – ISS NOTES ON DIGITAL PLATFORM (JULY 2023)

On July 17th, ISS shared with the C4D Coordinator an explanatory document to be attached to the C4D IMPLEMENTATION PLAN main document. The ISS contribution deals with “Implementation plan – ISS notes on Digital Platform”. The text of the document is reported here below as an additional support to implementers for better scheduling the actions to prepare and manage the digital platform.

Introduction to scope and content of the ISS notes on digital platform

Implementation plans must include an overview of the activities and related actions associated with the setup and use of the DIGITAL PLATFORM. These should aim to reach concrete objectives adapted to the context of the country/area and related to the general KPIs of a digital tool (availability, resilience to out-of-service events, usability, portability, fruition ...).

Additionally, data must be collected to support the evaluation of the DIGITAL PLATFORM and to provide information to fine-tune its architecture, contents and activities. The timely collection of the data will support the pilot implementers to correctly associate these actions to the other actions in their Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) cycles.

This document shortly describes the main actions needed for a successful implementation of the DIGITAL PLATFORM within C4D, namely:

1. Design and construction of the DIGITAL PLATFORM ARCHITECTURE
2. Preparation of the DIGITAL PLATFORM CONTENTS
3. Preparation of PLATFORM USER MANUALS and PLATFORM ASSESSMENT TOOL
4. Test and validation of the DIGITAL PLATFORM
5. Finalization and release of the DIGITAL PLATFORM
6. Identification of participants’ technical needs
7. Management of the DIGITAL PLATFORM during Round A intensive phase.
8. Assessment of the DIGITAL PLATFORM performance and implementation of the needed corrective actions
9. Management of the DIGITAL PLATFORM during Round A aftercare phase and Round B intensive phase.
10. Final assessment and optimization of the DIGITAL PLATFORM

Actions from 1 to 6 are preparatory actions, to be executed and concluded within the PLAN part of Round A PDSA cycle. Further, actions from 1 to 5 may be possibly repeated iteratively whenever a “STUDY and ACT” process will require it.

Please note: it is recommended that all PLATFORM tools and contents remain unchanged during each phase (intensive, aftercare, either in Round A or Round B): changes, if needed, should be always implemented before starting a new phase, unless major actions are required to not compromise the successful delivery of the C4D programme.

Please also note: it is strongly recommended that at least the Pilot Coordinator is trained to manage the DIGITAL PLATFORM early before the start of Round A intensive phase. Alternatively, another person of the team should be identified and trained for the purpose. All other team members will be then trained by this person.

Actions in detail

1. Design and construction of the DIGITAL PLATFORM ARCHITECTURE. It is a preparatory action, to be executed and concluded within the PLAN part of Round A PDSA cycle, and possibly repeated iteratively whenever a “STUDY and ACT” process will require it. Relevant documentation associated with this action can be found in the Deliverable 5.3. Activities within this action should especially focus on the following issues:
 - a. identification of resources and objectives: human and technical resources at the pilot implementation site should be clearly defined, as well as the C4D budget available for the DIGITAL PLATFORM. Especially relevant is also the clear definition of the “destination” of the PLATFORM, namely whether it is intended as a temporary solution, to be eventually replaced after the implementation of the pilot, or it rather represents the basis of a platform to be used beyond C4D (reasonably following optimization and consolidation). Finally, the needed time for the DIGITAL PLATFORM availability should be accurately estimated, to minimize the risks of delays in the pilot start
 - b. personnel recruitment and training: personnel to manage the DIGITAL PLATFORM, either full time employees or hired on purpose for C4D, should be identified as soon as possible, involved in the overall PLATFORM delivery process, and trained. Those persons should collaborate with the multidisciplinary Team and should be

- available along the C4D pilot implementation to support participants and the team via helpdesk activity and technical support
- c. PLATFORM retrieval/assessment/acquisition/adaptation/construction: one or more of those actions will be necessary to reach the final goal of preparing a reliable DIGITAL PLATFORM and render it available before the start of the C4D pilot. ISS surveys aimed at clearly understanding the state of the art and the needed actions at each implementation site. Information in Deliverable 5.3 hopefully help as well. From a specific technical point of view, and according the adopted solution, this action may refer to identification of and contractualization with external providers/suppliers/developers, internal activity of software development, bench-tests
2. Preparation of the DIGITAL PLATFORM CONTENTS. It is a preparatory action, to be executed and concluded within the PLAN part of Round A PDSA cycle, and possibly repeated iteratively whenever a “STUDY and ACT” process will require it. Relevant documentation associated with this action can be found in the Deliverable 5.3, the C4D document on publications and dissemination rules, the material shared by Voeding Leeft, the C4D document on recommended translations/adaptations. This action involves the multidisciplinary team, and at least includes:
 - a. the preliminary analysis of the VL material
 - b. translation/adaptation of the VL material: it is mandatory to be compliant with the C4D publications and dissemination rules
 - c. the preparation of new, purposely developed material; attention should be paid to the compliance with main technical requirements of the DIGITAL PLATFORM, in terms of format, storage size, internet resources, bandwidth usage; procedures should be defined for the material preparation and delivery, which should account for the validity and validation of the material, the internal (implementation site) and external (C4D Coordinators) supervision and the approval for release
 3. Preparation of PLATFORM USER MANUALS and PLATFORM ASSESSMENT TOOL. It is a preparatory action, to be executed and concluded within the PLAN part of Round A PDSA cycle, and possibly repeated iteratively whenever a “STUDY and ACT” process will require it. Main issues:
 - a. user manual for C4D DIGITAL PLATFORM manager: the person, or persons, with Administration rights and the responsibility of a secure functioning of the platform should rely on complete and clear written instructions, promptly available on

- demand (digitally available on the platform, and also stored and easily retrieved elsewhere); if the PLATFORM was already existing, the manual should already exist as well, but it is necessary to check for any needed integration, to comply with possible platform adaptations; alternatively, in case of a new construction of the platform, the manual must be prepared on purpose
- b. user manual for the multidisciplinary team: it should contain, at least, peculiar instructions on how to administer the multimedia contents and activities, schedule participants' activities, collect and store data, manage social interaction tools, supervise participants' contributions, update platform contents, deliver on-demand support. Preparation and availability of this user manual should follow the same key-requirements as mentioned at the previous point
 - c. user manual for participants: it should contain clear instructions on how to access and navigate the C4D PLATFORM, interact with participants and the team, use the multimedia contents, upload data and feedback, exploit each resource and activity of the platform. Besides the key-requirements already mentioned for the previous manuals, it is warmly recommended that this manual is very clear, supported by explanatory screenshots, simple, available on each page or section of the platform
 - d. structured checklist to monitor PLATFORM PERFORMANCE: the platform is an essential part of the best practice, thus it should be assessed as for its feasibility, usability and sustainability. Thus, it is extremely important to preliminary prepare a checklist to collect useful information on the way the platform performs during the pilot. The checklist should at least contain the following items: quantification of accesses and usage of the platform contents, resources and activities; quantification and characterization of requests for contents exploitation or technical support; monitoring of problems (malfunctioning, out-of-service, other) and problem-solving interventions; structured feedback from users.
4. Test and validation of the DIGITAL PLATFORM. It is a preparatory action, to be executed and concluded within the PLAN part of Round A PDSA cycle, and possibly repeated iteratively whenever a "STUDY and ACT" process will require it. This action should involve voluntary testers from the C4D multidisciplinary team, and few volunteers from the group of potential participants (alternatively, volunteers could be selected among other groups of patients, provided they are comparable with participants as for clinical, biological and behavioural status). Main issues:

- a. bench-test of technical functionalities: it is a verification process to be done by IT experts or purposely trained personnel who are well aware of the C4D purposes. Special attention should be paid to data security issues and GDPR compliance
 - b. identification and training of selected testers: volunteers should be clearly informed and trained to stress the platform functions to detect eventual missing features, too complex procedures, and overall usability of the platform
 - c. on-the-field tests (by the selected testers): testers should use the platform and report on eventual minor or major insufficient performance, accounting for usability and appropriateness; completeness and appropriateness of user manuals should be tested as well
5. Finalization and release of the DIGITAL PLATFORM. It is the last preparatory action, to be executed and concluded within the PLAN part of Round A PDSA cycle, and possibly repeated iteratively whenever a “STUDY and ACT” process will require it. At the end of this action the C4D DIGITAL PLATFORM shall be ready to be used in the pilot. Manuals shall be checked and eventually updated if changes occur during this action. Main issues:
- a. iterative approach: all previously described actions should be re-run according to the level of change required and implemented during this phase; in example, it is possible that only some contents are modified, which means no changes at the level of design, construction, training, manuals and so on; conversely, if a specific feature is found unsuitable or, even worse, data breaches are highlighted, the iteration should likely bring back to the very first action of this list
 - b. identification of acceptable limitations: since changes are strongly recommended to be avoided during the DO phases, it is possible that the DIGITAL PLATFORM is used without an acceptable subset of missing (minor) features; in this case each and every limitation of the platform shall be clearly described and reported in the manuals
 - c. informed consent for the use of the DIGITAL PLATFORM: besides the pilot study informed consent, an ad-hoc informed consent for the accreditation on and the use of the platform shall be prepared to be signed by the participants, stand-alone or as an integration of the study consent; the document shall clearly inform the users on the management, ownership and management of their digital data
6. Identification of participants’ technical needs: before starting the DO phase of the pilot, it is recommended to investigate whether the enrolled participants need technical

resources to properly use and exploit the platform, and eventually define the delivery strategy. The needed technical resources may include:

- a. devices to be replaced (i.e. available at the time of enrolment but damaged, or no longer suitable/available)
 - b. a more stable internet connection
 - c. tools to improve the quality of the interaction like removable webcams, more comfortable headphones,...
7. Management of the DIGITAL PLATFORM during Round A intensive phase. The action will take place during the DO phase of Round A intensive phase. Management occurs at different levels and with different purposes by the following actors: the platform manager, the multidisciplinary team coordinator, the multidisciplinary team, the IT support team (if not included in the multidisciplinary team). Management activities shall be documented at each level, through structured checklists or by means of free reports. Briefly:
- a. the platform manager monitors the platform and solve (or alerts reference persons for solving) eventual faults or malfunctioning
 - b. the team coordinator monitors the activities on the platform, alerts the technical support when needed, coordinates the team activities, alerts the proper expert in the team to address peculiar problems, on-demand requests, or approval of participants' contents
 - c. the multidisciplinary team monitors the activities on the platform, delivers planned contributions and on-demand support, supervise data collection and manage the data to monitor and modulate the C4D programme, eventually integrates contents, interacts with manager, coordinator and the IT support team
 - d. the IT support team delivers on-demand technical support, monitors the technical performance of the platform, solve (or interact with the manager to solve) technical problems
8. Assessment of the DIGITAL PLATFORM performance and implementation of the needed corrective actions. This action occurs during the STUDY and ACT phases of Round A, and during the overlapping PLAN phase of Round B. It basically focusses on the following issues:
- a. completion and analysis of the checklist on the DIGITAL PLATFORM performance
 - b. identification of possible corrective actions
 - c. iteration of actions from 1 to 5 (from platform design to finalization)

- d. new execution of step 6 (identification and delivery of possibly needed technical resources) before Round B start
9. Management of the DIGITAL PLATFORM during Round A aftercare phase and Round B intensive phase (DO). This action occurs during Round A aftercare phase and Round B intensive phase, which partially overlap one another. Management of the DIGITAL PLATFORM does not differ between intensive and aftercare phase but for the reduced scheduling of activities and intensity of use of the platform itself by the participants. Main actions replicate those listed at step 7
10. Final assessment and optimization of the DIGITAL PLATFORM. This final action is intended to start from March 2025. Besides the actions listed at step 8, an overall deep analysis of feedback from all users is recommended, as well as the delivery of conclusions relevant to understand the platform sustainability. In particular, each country will elaborate on the digital solution adopted during Round A and Round B, to investigate whether it may represent or not the core of a long-term solution to be locally implemented and maintained. Among the several aspects to elaborate, worth to mention are the data security and the compliance with GDPR and related local laws, the compliance with accessibility, equity and diversity, and ethical principles, the acceptability, the usability and the economic sustainability.